

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

CONSIDERATIONS OF THE EFFECT OF ARMED CONFLICTS ON ACCOUNTING ESTIMATE OF FIXED ASSETS

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Abstract

Armed aggression in Ukraine emphasized on reconsidering the accounting assumptions and approaches toward recognition, classification and measurement of the fixed assets that suffered physical damage or destruction as well as undergone deuteriation in usefulness due to worsening external environment. In the article the author studies the specifics of accounting estimate of enterprise's fixed assets in terms of uncertainty driven by the armed conflicts. The number of accounting implications with regard to fixed assets accounting and measurement were considered in particular derecognition of fixed assets as a result of damage or destruction, revaluation or testing fixed assets for impairment, accounting for repair of partially damaged assets, etc. The author also provided a comparative analysis of cost and revaluation models applied for accounting of the fixed assets. Additionally, the author proposed methodological approaches for accounting estimate of the fixed assets in wartime depending on such factors as the condition of the assets, level of damage suffered, ability to exercise control over the fixed asset, feasibility to conduct repair of the damaged assets etc.

Keywords: cost model, revaluation model, impairment, revaluation, loss of control, going concern, fixed assets

Being the element of the accounting method a valuation results in providing a quantities estimate of the worth (value) to assets, liabilities, financial flows (revenues, expenses) of the enterprise in monetary terms [1, 2]. The consequences of armed aggression of Russian Federation in Ukraine unleashed on February 24, 2022, actualize exploration of accounting implications, inter alia pose the issue of reliable and unbiased estimate of enterprise's assets. In turn fixed assets occupies a major position of total assets of the enterprise being a mean that over a long term ensure the transformation of input resources (raw materials, energy, labor, services) into finished goods or services that embody economic benefits. Therefore, the aim of this article is to explore the specifics of accounting estimate of enterprise's fixed assets in terms of uncertainty driven by the armed conflicts.

Armed aggression resulted in a set of negative consequences for the physical condition, value and expectation of further use of fixed assets of domestic enterprises. The exact figures are unclear yet, but according to the analysis of Kyiv School on Economics the total amount of actual losses to Ukrainian enterprises might reach a level of USD 13 bn as of the beginning of 2023 [3]. In the economic context the accounting estimate of fixed assets suffered from the effect of the armed aggression in the following ways:

- negative changes in external economic environment worsened expectation of market participants of the use of the assets in the future periods (e.g., increase idle time, decrease in residual useful life's);
- loss of control, joint control or ability to exercise significant influence over the assets as a result of occupation of the territories;

- assets undergone physical destruction or damage due to conduct of ground military operations, bombing, shelling, etc.

The literature review of recent studies indicated an importance of implication of the war on the accounting of enterprise's fixed assets. Exploring the issue of fixed assets accounting in wartime conditions, V. Zhuk, Y. Bezdushna and E. Popko came to the conclusion that in order to respond to the war circumstances in the context of property management, Ukrainian enterprises need to make changes to the accounting policies regarding fixed assets depreciation [4]. When studying the consequences of armed aggression and the occupation of territories, on the accounting estimate of fixed assets, D. Hrycysheh and others concluded that valuation of fixed for accounting purposes should consider the following: (1) difficulties for reconciling the consequences of armed aggression with specific assets, (2) unsettled issues regarding identification and recognition of the consequences of armed aggression in accounting at the level of accounting legislation, (3) difficulties of documenting the consequences of armed aggression due to the absence or limited access to the fixed assets [5]. The author has concluded that the impact of mentioned factors has the of accounting implication to the value of fixed assets in financial statements:

- review of the assumptions on accounting policies related to fixed assets measurement (e.g., method of depreciation, useful lives, the amount of liquidation value);
- review of the assumptions regarding the recognitions of fixed assets (e.g., review the ability to exercise control, joint control or significant influence over the assets);

- review of basic accounting concept for valuing fixed assets (e.g., whether the enterprise complies with going concern, so that the asset might be accounted in accordance with this assumption);
- recognition of losses as a result of damages or destruction of fixed assets;
- decrease in the books value of fixed assets as a result of revaluations or impairments depending on the method for accounting of fixed assets (cost or revaluation model).

When studying the accounting valuation of fixed assets, it is important to consider the methodological aspects in more detail. The description of the approach toward accounting of fixed assets in the context of initial recognition, calculation of historical cost, the choice of an accounting model and the definition of an accounting estimate as of the end of reporting period is stipulated in IAS 16 "Fixed Assets" [6]. In accordance with mentioned methodological standard, the basis for the initial recognition of the value of fixed assets is the sum of historical costs for their acquisition, transportation and bringing to a state suitable for operation. Simultaneously, at initial recognition, the object of fixed assets must meet criterias of controllability, possibility of quantitative valuation and presence of economic benefits from future use. In other words, at the moment of initial recognition the cost approach mentioned in the International Valuation Standards serves as the basis for determining the cost of fixed assets [7].

As the usefulness of fixed assets is realized during the long term the accounting model for reflecting changes in the value of asset over time should be in place (the cost model or the revaluation model). In general, the value of assets can be considered, firstly, from the standpoint of the cost of the resources needed to create or acquire the asset (labor theory of value), secondly, from the standpoint of the value of cash flows

and other economic benefits that the asset is expected to generate in the future (neoclassical economic theory). The cost model is based on the principles of the first approach (the cost of the resources needed to create the asset), while as the revaluation model – on the second approach (the amount of economic benefits from the use of the asset). The results on comparative analysis of the two models in mentioned in the table 1. Thus, the accounting valuation of fixed assets can be viewed as a historical original cost in the past, net book or fair value in the present, and liquidation value in the future.

According to the cost model at the end of each reporting period the enterprise's management must assess whether there are criterias of impairment. If such indications exist, it is necessary to estimate recoverable amount for such assets. In case of armed aggression there are several criterias of a decrease in the usefulness of the fixed assets (e.g., negative change in the market and economic environment, increase in market interest rates, physical damage of the asset). Therefore, it is likely that the recoverable amount of the asset will have to be estimated. The latter asset is the higher of two values: fair value less costs of disposal and value in use. If case the recoverable amount is less than the net book value of the fixed asset, the difference is recognized as an impairment in the income statement.

The similar situation is with the model of revaluation of fixed assets. The negative changes in external environment should most likely cause the need for revaluation of fixed assets (even for the assets that were not physically damaged due to the armed aggression). The revaluation results (change in the fair value of fixed assets) is reflected by an increase / decrease in the net book value of the fixed assets, changes in revaluation reserve, and if the amount revaluation reserve is insufficient to cover decrease in value, the difference is recognized in the income statement.

Comparative analysis of the models for accounting of enterprise's fixed assets

Features	Cost model	Revaluation model
Underlying principle of the model	Accounting of the assets at the lower of historical depreciated cost (net book value) or recoverable amount (the higher of fair value less costs of disposal and value in use).	Accounting of the asset at fair value or at an amount close to the fair value. In case of the presence of the active market the fair value should correspond to fair market value.
Responsibility of conducting revaluation as of the reporting date	In case of presence of impairment triggering events, the company's management build the model for testing the assets of cash generating unit for impairment. It is also possible to contract advisor for preparation of the impairment model.	To conduct fixed asset revaluation company's management must contract independent external valuer possessing relevant industry experience and professional qualifications,
Cases for conducting impairment or revaluation	Impairment testing of fixed assets in conducted in case of presence of certain triggering events (e.g., deterioration or physical damage to the asset, fall in market demand, inflationary environment, rise in interest rates).	The revaluation is carried out at the discretion of the management, so that of net book value of fixed assets does not differ significantly from the fair value as of the reporting date.
Comparative indicator for book value	The recoverable amount is used for comparison with the latest net book value (historical depreciated cost). The recoverable amount which is the higher of fair value less costs of disposal and value in use. Impairment analysis is conducted be cash generating units.	Revaluation results is compared with the latest net book value (previous revaluation adjusted for the depreciation expense).
Accounting for change in historical cost	The historical cost is constant, instead the amount of accumulated depreciation is adjusted to account for impairment.	The historical cost is adjusted to account for revaluation results.
Accounting for change in net book value	The book value can be increased to the value that was before the impairment of assets (reversal of impairment).	On the revaluation date, the net book value approximates the fair market value.

Sources: prepared by the author based on the analysis of [6], [8], [9].

During the armed aggression, it is not uncommon to experience physical destruction or damage to assets such as fixed assets, inventories, investment properties, etc. Accordingly, such assets do not meet the criterias for definition of an asset due to the absence of future economic benefits and subsequently should not be reflected in the financial statements. If the assets are partially damaged, it is necessary to consider conduct identification procedures to assess the technical feasibility and economical relevance of the repair of damages assets as well as consider the impairment of such damaged assets accordingly (refer to pic. 1). In case of damaged assets repair the author has concluded that the following steps should be considered:

- recognition of expenses in income statement for the amount of depreciated value of damaged components of the asset (partial impairment of the asset). If it

is impossible to derive the value of damaged components the value of damages assets might be decreased proportionally to the level of damage determined based of their technical observation of the damaged asset;

- accounting of the cost of new components as well as other expenses (payroll, services) required to conduct asset repair to return it to previous working condition. The enterprise should choose whether to capitalize such expenses or expense in the current period. The author has concluded that the choice largely depends on the level of damage caused to the asset and the specifics of repair (e.g., replacing the full component of the asset or conducting of maintenance repair);
- accounting for materials obtained during liquidation of the consequences of asset damage (if any).

Pic. 1. Approaches for accounting estimate of the fixed assets in wartime

Sources: prepared by the author based on the analysis of [10], [11]

Regarding fixed assets located in uncontrolled (occupied) territories the author concluded that two options might be generally accepted: either to completely remove these assets from the accounts (e.g., if there is information that such assets were destroyed or significantly damaged) or to impair such assets in full due to loss of control over the assets, and subsequently inability of use of such assets and reap economic benefits. The author believes that if there is no reliable information about the damage or destruction of fixed assets located on uncontrolled territories the second option with accrual of impairment is more justified, since we there is ability to reverse the impairment after regaining the control over the assets.

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